

Assessing the impact of non-pharmaceutical (NPI) interventions and the role of mutations on the SARS-CoV-2 Virus spread in India using a discrete renewal process

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(a) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state Maharashtra with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 1: Maharashtra

(a) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state Punjab with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 2: Punjab

(a) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state Karnataka with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 3: Karnataka

(a) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state Uttarpradesh with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 4: Uttar Pradesh

(a) Plot for The state Gujrat with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Gujrat with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Gujrat with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for the state Gujrat respect to R_t for With mutation

(e) Plot for the state Gujrat respect to α for With mutation

(f) Plot for the state Gujrat respect to R_0 for With mutation

Figure S 5: Gujrat

(a) Plot for The state TamilNadu with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state TamilNadu with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state TamilNadu with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for the state TamilNadu respect to R_t for With mutation

(e) Plot for the state TamilNadu respect to α for With mutation

(f) Plot for the state TamilNadu respect to R_0 for With mutation

Figure S 6: Tamilnadu

(a) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state Kerala with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 7: Kerala

(a) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to R_t for without mutation

(b) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to α for without mutation

(c) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to R_0 for without mutation

(d) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to R_t for with mutation

(e) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to α for with mutation

(f) Plot for The state West Bengal with respect to R_0 for with mutation

Figure S 8: West Bengal

Parameter	State	Mutation or Without Mutation	Value	Band Range
R_0	West Bengal	Without Mutation	1.028	(1.016 - 1.040)
R_0	West Bengal	With Mutation	1.95	(1.1 - 5.1)
R_t	West Bengal	With Mutation	1.006	(0.98 - 1.02)
R_t	West Bengal	Without Mutation	0.9944	(0.9433 - 1.0248)
R_0	Kerala	Without Mutation	1.111	(1.031 - 1.209)
R_0	Kerala	With Mutation	1.687	(1.38 - 1.857)
R_t	Kerala	With Mutation	0.95	(0.978 - 1.02)
R_t	Kerala	Without Mutation	0.788794	(0.31002 - 1.106619)
R_0	Gujrat	Without Mutation	1.024	(1.012 - 1.029)
R_0	Gujrat	With Mutation	1.024	(1.015 - 1.029)
R_t	Gujrat	With Mutation	1.027	(1.-11 - 1.028)
R_t	Gujrat	Without Mutation	0.9967	(0.9609 - 1.01228)
R_0	Punjab	Without Mutation	1.050	(1.024 - 1.102)
R_0	Punjab	With Mutation	1.1029	(1.048 - 1.142)
R_t	Punjab	With Mutation	1.10288	(1.077 - 1.127)
R_t	Punjab	Without Mutation	1.0488	(1.0366 - 1.655)
R_0	Maharashtra	Without Mutation	1.027	(1.018 - 1.037)
R_0	Maharashtra	With Mutation	2.5	(2.3 - 18)
R_t	Maharashtra	With Mutation	1.025	(1.016 - 1.036)
R_t	Maharashtra	Without Mutation	0.5276356	(0.0001249 - 0.9501709)
R_0	Karnataka	Without Mutation	1.033	(1.027 - 1.0399)
R_0	Karnataka	With Mutation	1.121	(1.033 - 1.7)
R_t	Karnataka	With Mutation	1.0264	(0.9835 - 1.0436)
R_t	Karnataka	Without Mutation	0.9672	(0.8836 - 1.0243)
R_0	Uttarpradesh	Without Mutation	1.045	(1.033 - 1.058)
R_0	Uttarpradesh	With Mutation	1.127	(1.069 - 1.215)
R_t	Uttarpradesh	With Mutation	1.041	(1.021 - 1.055)
R_t	Uttarpradesh	Without Mutation	0.9523	(0.8407 - 1.0125)
R_0	Tamil Nadu	Without Mutation	1.03	(1.014 - 1.036)
R_0	Tamil Nadu	With Mutation	1.032	(1.016 - 1.054)
R_t	Tamil Nadu	With Mutation	1.020	(1.009868 - 1.027354)
R_t	Tamil Naduh	Without Mutation	1.0114	(0.9747 - 1.25)

Table S 1: R_0 , R_t , values for each states with mutation and without mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Punjab	Market	0.0765857933
	Interstate	0.0015032323
	Intrastate	0.0008592614
	Mut 3	0.25115648567
	Mut 6	0.25014128633
	Mut 9	0.257639598
	Mut 14	0.0003593624
	Mut 15	0.1990800546
	Mut 35	0.000274242928
	Mut 39	0.0477600361

Table S 2: Punjab α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Uttar Pradesh	Market	0.0005388315
	Interstate	0.0005184791
	Intrastate	0.0006990124
	Mut 31	0.0065007381
	Mut 44	0.0037391518
	Mut 174	0.0115539591
	Mut 187	0.1249861450
	Mut 259	0.0070586987
	Mut 428	0.0070744101
	Mut 431	0.0043313216

Table S 3: Uttar Pradesh α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Kerala	Market	0.183601
	Interstate	0.045758
	Intrastate	0.027633
	Mut7	0.0341167
	Mut9	0.0079202
	Mut10	0.056189
	Mut11	0.0098345
	Mut13	0.012345
	Mut15	0.045612
	Mut18	0.067890
	Mut29	0.023456
	Mut36	0.00432012
	Mut38	0.00721901
	Mut40	0.0567389
	Mut41	0.034567
	Mut43	0.018423
	Mut45	0.056789
	Mut50	0.0098345
	Mut54	0.0112335
	Mut60	0.00045642
	Mut62	0.0047900
	Mut64	0.033456
	Mut67	0.0089012
	Mut68	0.447821
	Mut74	0.0078901
	Mut77	0.056789
	Mut79	0.034567
	Mut82	0.0068123
	Mut83	0.0016759
	Mut84	0.0098345
	Mut93	0.00131345
	Mut97	0.046442
	Mut98	0.0067590
	Mut103	0.0254856
	Mut105	0.0097543
	Mut106	0.007643
	Mut112	0.0046789
	Mut113	0.021458
	Mut114	0.0078454
	Mut118	0.001533
	Mut126	0.009344
	Mut128	0.008612
	Mut130	0.0456
	Mut131	0.008652
Mut132	0.001534	
Mut133	0.0089012	
Mut134	0.00078901	
Mut138	0.009534789	
Mut164	0.034657	
Mut166	0.02753	
Mut167	0.05769	
Mut183	0.00635	
Mut184	0.017667	
Mut197	0.04764	
Mut199	0.00543	
Mut209	0.02356	
Mut223	0.007412	
Mut235	0.00784531	
Mut236	0.0056789	
Mut256	0.034567	
Mut299	0.0078123	
Mut308	0.056789	
Mut320	0.0098345	
Mut332	0.012345	
Mut338	0.045612	
Mut353	0.0067890	
Mut355	0.023456	
Mut361	0.0084692	
Mut384	0.00765901	
Mut390	0.056789	
Mut494	0.034567	
Mut496	0.0076533	
Mut499	0.056789	
Mut500	0.098345	
Mut509	0.012345	
Mut539	0.045612	
Mut609	0.0067670	
Mut724	0.023456	
Mut778	0.0085432	
Mut998	0.0078901	
Mut1344	0.056789	

Table S 4: Kerala α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Maharashtra	Market	0.387609653
	Interstate	0.122700907
	Intrastate	0.019219180
	Mut 31	0.048008142
	Mut 33	0.063609827
	Mut 47	0.009253089
	Mut 51	0.126909571
	Mut 91	0.032240017
	Mut 137	0.062513911
	Mut 138	0.011825214
	Mut 140	0.008948156
	Mut 160	0.018214430
	Mut 190	0.056084927
	Mut 215	0.010033719
	Mut 252	0.009566597
	Mut 312	0.025200497
	Mut 315	0.010368422
	Mut 317	0.009347521
	Mut 360	1.236996710
	Mut 378	0.009219394
	Mut 384	0.010973440
	Mut 440	0.061540868
	Mut 441	0.009388599
	Mut 443	0.009603974
	Mut 445	0.009045041
	Mut 796	0.010424165
	Mut 797	0.009377054
	Mut 816	0.026665355
	Mut 869	0.066649144
	Mut 917	0.645099011
	Mut 927	0.027048164
	Mut 943	0.057952061
	Mut 953	0.009845674
Mut 977	0.011615179	
Mut 985	0.010798475	
Mut 992	0.076063877	

Table S 5: Maharashtra α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Tamil Nadu	Market	0.0072999640
	Interstate	0.0009619719
	Intrastate	0.0007854808
	Mut 7	0.0013147135
	Mut 11	0.0015162284
	Mut 66	0.0022863502
	Mut 84	0.0012386405
	Mut 750	0.0019410614

Table S 6: Tamil Nadu α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Karnataka	Market	0.001442592
	Interstate	0.001304051
	Intrastate	0.001495982
	Mut 54	0.001998624
	Mut 58	0.002990413
	Mut 74	0.002252846
	Mut 92	0.003972159
	Mut 93	0.002639403
	Mut 100	0.002007517
	Mut 123	0.001997574
	Mut 127	0.002300310
	Mut 133	0.001930729
	Mut 241	0.001808161
	Mut 255	0.002060412
	Mut 292	0.001904035
	Mut 293	0.001904035
	Mut 300	0.002257622
	Mut 333	0.09883520
	Mut 546	0.001976601
	Mut 511	0.001976601
	Mut 542	0.003409617
	Mut 552	0.001929339
	Mut 612	0.002000348
	Mut 641	0.007368808
	Mut 725	0.001961796
	Mut 728	0.0031116749
	Mut 761	0.003832304
	Mut 820	0.004241267
	Mut 864	0.004241267

Table S 7: Karnataka α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
West Bengal	Market	0.0007980341
	Interstate	0.0006409
	Intrastate	0.0003765
	Mut 61	0.00291
	Mut 102	0.001911
	Mut 257	0.0013932
	Mut 279	0.6448923
Mut 732	0.0020693	

Table S 8: West Bengal α values with mutation

State	Mutation ID	α -Value with mutation
Gujarat	Market	0.0023963
	Interstate	0.0031769
	Intrastate	0.008321
	Mut 70	0.0011306
	Mut 386	0.0008490

Table S 9: Gujarat α values with mutation

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Maharashtra	Mut31	5'UTR	G124T				Observed in 41 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by USA and India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut33	5'UTR	C147T				Observed in 108 countries. Most prevalent in USA, followed by Canada and UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut47	5'UTR	G252T				Observed in 80 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Slovenia and Japan.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut51	ORF1a	C364T	nsp1			Observed in 96 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, France and India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut91	ORF1a	C981T	nsp2	A59V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 76 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Germany.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut137	ORF1a	C1613T	nsp2	L270F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 96 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut138	ORF1a	T1626G	nsp2	L274R	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 25 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut140	ORF1a	G1681T	nsp2	E292D	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 74 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Mexico and India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut160	ORF1a	C1919A	nsp2	L372I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 43 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut215	ORF1a	A2712G	nsp2	K636R	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 60 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut252	ORF1a	G3340T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 120 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Canada and Japan.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut312	ORF1a	T4273G	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 26 countries. Most prevalent in India followed by France and USA.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut315	ORF1a	G4289T	nsp3	A524S	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 42 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Japan, UK and Canada.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut317	ORF1a	C4320T	nsp3	A534V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 133 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut360	ORF1a	C5167T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 87 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Denmark.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut378	ORF1a	C5467T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 114 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut440	ORF1a	A6497G	nsp3	K1260E	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 61 countries. Most prevalent in France followed by UK, South Korea, India and Ghana.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut441	ORF1a	T6511C	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 50 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by South Korea and UK.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut443	ORF1a	G6532T	nsp3	E1271D	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 59 countries. Most prevalent in USA.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut445	ORF1a	C6539T,Y	nsp3	H1274Y	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 164 countries. Most prevalent in USA, followed by UK and India.	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut796	ORF1a	G12167T	nsp8	V26F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 47 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India and Germany.	Not found in literature

Table S 10: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomics location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Maharashtra	Mut977	ORF1a	C15895T	nsp12		Synonymous	Observed in 80 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Denmark and UK	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut979	ORF1a	T12181C	nsp8		Synonymous	Observed in 56 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and India	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut816	ORF1a	T12535C	nsp8		Synonymous	Observed in 54 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and India	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut869	ORF1a	G13843A	nsp12	D135N	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 33 countries. Most prevalent in USA	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut917	ORF1a	G14829T	nsp12	M463I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 114 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut927	ORF1a	T15096C	nsp12		Synonymous	Observed in 148 countries. Most prevalent in Germany followed by USA, UK, Sweden and Canada	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut953	ORF1a	C15656T	nsp12	T739I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 140 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Denmark and Japan	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut985	ORF1a	G15982T	nsp12	V848L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 85 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India	Not found in literature
Maharashtra	Mut992	ORF1a	C16134T	nsp12		Synonymous	Observed in 59 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut7	5'UTR	C66A,T				Observed in 51 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut9	5'UTR	C92T				Observed in 101 countries. Most prevalent in USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut10	5'UTR	G94T				Observed in 81 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut11	5'UTR	G102A				Observed in 48 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut13	5'UTR	T144C				Observed in 57 countries. Most prevalent in USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut15	5'UTR	G174T				Observed in 156 countries. Most prevalent in USA and South Africa followed by UK and France	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut18	5'UTR	G204T				Observed in 91 countries. Most prevalent in Denmark and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut29	ORF1a	G347A	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 112 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Germany and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut36	ORF1a	C556T	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 114 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut38	ORF1a	G587A	nsp1	V108I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 71 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, France and Canada	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut40	ORF1a	G596A	nsp1	V111M	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 61 countries. Most prevalent in UK and USA followed by Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut41	ORF1a	T606C	nsp1	I114T	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 68 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by France, UK and Australia	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut43	ORF1a	C622T	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 88 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, France, Germany, Japan and Brazil	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut45	ORF1a	C664T	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 116 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Ireland	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut50	ORF1a	C706Y	nsp1			Observed in 10 countries. Most prevalent in UK and USA followed by India	Not found in literature

Table S 11: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Kerala	Mut54	ORF1a	C745T	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 151 countries. Most prevalent in France and USA followed by Germany and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut60	ORF1a	G872T	nsp2	D23Y	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 72 countries. Most prevalent in France and USA followed by Japan and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut62	ORF1a	C878T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 106 countries. Most prevalent in France and USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut64	ORF1a	C913T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 197 countries. Most prevalent in UK and USA followed by Germany, Sweden, Denmark and Japan	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut67	ORF1a	A929G	nsp2	I42V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 107 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut68	ORF1a	C936T	nsp2	T44I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 137 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Japan	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut74	ORF1a	G1055A	nsp2	D84N	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 50 countries. Most prevalent in USA and China followed by Canada	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut77	ORF1a	C1108T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 101 countries. Most prevalent in Brazil followed by USA and Peru	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut79	ORF1a	C1113T	nsp2	T103I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 73 countries. Most prevalent in Peru followed by Brazil	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut82	ORF1a	C1191T	nsp2	P129L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 193 countries. Most prevalent in India and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut83	ORF1a	A1208G	nsp2	M135V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 53 countries. Most prevalent in India followed by USA, China and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut84	ORF1a	C1218T	nsp2	S138L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 171 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut93	ORF1a	C1385T	nsp2	H194Y	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 137 countries. Most prevalent in Denmark and USA followed by UK and Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut97	ORF1a	T1432A	nsp2	N209K	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 29 countries. Most prevalent in Brazil followed by Canada, Denmark, South Korea and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut98	ORF1a	C1437T	nsp2	S211F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 108 countries. Most prevalent in USA and Australia followed by Japan and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut103	ORF1a	C1498T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 121 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Canada and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut105	ORF1a	C1519T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 115 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Germany and Canada	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut106	ORF1a	C1567T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 106 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Canada, Italy, Panama and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut112	ORF1a	C1762T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 63 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Japan, Germany, UK, France and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut113	ORF1a	G1772T	nsp2	V323F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 45 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Ireland and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut114	ORF1a	A1807G	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 105 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Canada, France and Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut118	ORF1a	G1843C	nsp2	Q346H	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 20 countries. Most prevalent in USA and India followed by France	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut126	ORF1a	C1959T	nsp2	A385V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 88 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut128	ORF1a	T1984G	nsp2	I393M	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 19 countries. Most prevalent in USA and Mexico, followed by UK and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut130	ORF1a	C2040T	nsp2	T412I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 118 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature

Table S 12: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Kerala	Mut131	ORF1a	C2061T	nsp2	A419V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 140 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Mexico	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut132	ORF1a	C2062T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 145 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut133	ORF1a	A2066G	nsp2	I421V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 46 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut134	ORF1a	A2069G	nsp2	T422A	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 68 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK followed by India and Canada	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut138	ORF1a	G2144K(G or T)	nsp2			Observed in 20 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and Denmark	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut164	ORF1a	C2700T	nsp2	T632I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 86 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Columbia and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut166	ORF1a	A2730C	nsp3	K4T	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 28 countries. Most prevalent in France followed by UK and USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut167	ORF1a	G2764T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 86 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and Brazil	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut183	ORF1a	G3179A	nsp3	E154K	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 69 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Germany, Australia and Japan	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut184	ORF1a	G3206T	nsp3	D163Y	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 110 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut197	ORF1a	G3403T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 98 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut199	ORF1a	A3456G	nsp3	Y246C	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 70 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Spain and South Korea	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut209	ORF1a	A3647G	nsp3	I310V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 63 countries. Most prevalent in Spain followed by USA and India	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut223	ORF1a	C3885T,*	nsp3	P389L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 95 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India and France	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut235	ORF1a	G4144A	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 62 countries. Most prevalent in UK and Australia followed by Germany, India and Japan	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut236	ORF1a	G4162T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 105 countries. Most prevalent in USA and India followed by Germany and UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut256	ORF1a	C4655T	nsp3	R646W	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 97 countries. Most prevalent in USA and India followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut299	ORF1a	T5619C	nsp3	I967T	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 105 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut308	ORF1a	C5806T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 133 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut320	ORF1a	T6104*,G	nsp3	Y1129D	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 9 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut332	ORF1a	C6310A	nsp3	S1197R	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 40 countries. Most prevalent in India and South Korea	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut338	ORF1a	A6360G	nsp3	D1214G	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 50 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Brazil and France	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut353	ORF1a	G6617A	nsp3	G1300S	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 53 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK followed by France and Germany	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut355	ORF1a	G6642T	nsp3	G1308V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 37 countries. Most prevalent in Canada	Not found in literature

Table S 13: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Kerala	Mut361	ORF1a	C6751T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 77 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK, followed by India and Turkey.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut384	ORF1a	T7462C	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 37 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Turkey.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut390	ORF1a	T7714C	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 91 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and France.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut494	ORF1a	C9803T	nsp4		Synonymous	Observed in 278 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Germany.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut496	ORF1a	C9857T	nsp4		Synonymous	Observed in 151 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Canada, Norway, France and Peru.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut499	ORF1a	G9928T	nsp4	M458I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 86 countries. Most prevalent in USA.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut500	ORF1a	T9941Y (C or T)	nsp4			Observed in 5 countries. Most prevalent in Switzerland.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut509	ORF1a	C10186T	nsp5		Synonymous	Observed in 100 countries. Most prevalent in Germany followed by USA and UK.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut539	ORF1a	C11003Y (C or T)	nsp6			Observed in 28 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Denmark, India and Canada.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut609	ORF1a	C12973T	nsp9		Synonymous	Observed in 89 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Germany.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut724	ORF1b	C16762T	nsp13	L176F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 86 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Denmark, France and Japan.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut778	ORF1b	C18166T	nsp14	P43S	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 106 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Canada, Germany, France, India and Italy.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut998	S	C23271A	Spike	A570V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 194 countries. Most prevalent in USA, UK followed by Germany and Sweden.	Not found in literature
Kerala	Mut1344	N	G28378T	N(Nucleocapsid)		Synonymous	Observed in 159 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK followed by Germany, Sweden, India, Brazil and Norway.	Not found in literature
Gujarat	Mut70	ORF1a	C1329A	nsp2	T175N	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 61 countries. Most prevalent in Japan, followed by France and USA.	Not found in literature
Gujarat	Mut386	ORF1a	G8102T	nsp3	V1795F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 37 countries. Most prevalent in USA and Japan followed by UK and Slovenia.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut31	ORF1a	G713R	nsp1			Observed in 13 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and India.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut44	ORF1a	C1267T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 169 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut174	ORF1a	G7996A	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 54 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA, Germany and India.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut187	ORF1a	C8664T	nsp4	T37I	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 102 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and Sweden.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut259	ORF1b	G13850A	nsp12	G137D	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 21 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA, Canada, France, India and Japan.	Not found in literature
Uttar Pradesh	Mut428	S	C24784T	Spike		Synonymous	Observed in 102 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Germany and Sweden.	Not found in literature

Table S 14: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Punjab	Mut3	5'UTR	G210T				Observed in 211 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in literature
Punjab	Mut6	ORF1a	G374A	nsp1	E37K	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 75 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA, Netherlands and Germany	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut9	ORF1a	G407A	nsp1	D48N	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 64 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Canada, Germany and India	Not found in literature
Punjab	Mut14	ORF1a	C913T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 197 countries. Most prevalent in UK and USA followed by Germany, Sweden, Denmark and Japan	
Punjab	Mut15	ORF1a	C934T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 128 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut16	ORF1a	C1076T	nsp2	P91S	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 84 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Germany and India	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut20	ORF1a	C1385T	nsp2	H194Y	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 135 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Denmark and UK	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut35	ORF1a	C2644T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 122 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Germany, Canada, Brazil and Sweden	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut39	ORF1a	A3064G	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 55 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Germany	Not found in Literature
Punjab	Mut52	ORF1a	A3951G	nsp3	D411G	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 67 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, South Korea and Japan	Not found in Literature
Tamil Nadu	Mut7	5'UTR	C100T				Observed in 122 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Sweden	Not found in Literature
Tamil Nadu	Mut11	5'UTR	G210T				Observed in 211 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in Literature
Tamil Nadu	Mut69	ORF1a	G1161K	nsp2			Observed in 5 countries	Not found in Literature
Tamil Nadu	Mut84	ORF1a	G2095A	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 96 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and France	Not found in Literature
Tamil Nadu	Mut750	N	G28712A	N (Nucleocapsid)	G147S	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 63 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Japan and Brazil	Not found in Literature
West Bengal	Mut61	ORF1a	C799T	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 109 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Germany and France	Not found in Literature
West Bengal	Mut102	ORF1a	A1622G	nsp2	I273V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 47 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Denmark and India	Not found in Literature
West Bengal	Mut256	ORF1a	G5558T	nsp3	V947L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 48 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by South Korea, India and Peru	Not found in Literature
West Bengal	Mut279	ORF1a	C6310A	nsp3	S1197R	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 136 countries. Most prevalent in Germany and USA followed by Switzerland	Not found in Literature
West Bengal	Mut732	ORF1b	C18508T	nsp14	L157F	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 143 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Sweden	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut29	5'UTR	C106T				Observed in 133 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK	Not found in Literature

Table S 15: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations

State	Mutation Number	Region	Mutation	Protein region	Amino acid change	Mutation type	Distribution	Functional effect
Karnataka	Mut54	ORF1a	A460G	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 72 countries. Most prevalent in China followed by USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut58	ORF1a	A548G	nsp1	I95V	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 65 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA, Germany and Egypt.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut74	ORF1a	C835T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 143 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut92	ORF1a	C1060T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 137 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by South Korea and UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut93	ORF1a	A1119T	nsp2	Q105L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 21 countries. Most prevalent in USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut100	ORF1a	C1267T, Y	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 169 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by India.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut123	ORF1a	C1912T	nsp2		Synonymous	Observed in 166 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Brazil.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut133	ORF1a	T1978*, C	nsp1		Synonymous	Observed in 62 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by USA and France.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut241	ORF1a	A3314G	nsp3	T199A	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 49 countries. Most prevalent in Mexico followed by USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut255	ORF1a	A3652G	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 47 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK and Bangladesh.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut292	ORF1a	G4444A	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 65 countries. Most prevalent in USA and UK followed by France, Netherlands and India.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut300	ORF1a	A4659G	nsp3		Nonsynonymous	Observed in 91 countries. Most prevalent in Sweden followed by USA and UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut333	ORF1a	C5170*, T	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 92 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by Spain and USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut346	ORF1a	A5608G	nsp3		Synonymous	Observed in 80 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK, Canada and Brazil.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut511	ORF1a	C9559T	nsp4		Synonymous	Observed in 153 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Brazil and India.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut542	ORF1a	C10336T	nsp5		Synonymous	Observed in 94 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Denmark, UK and Germany.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut552	ORF1a	C10702T	nsp5		Synonymous	Observed in 140 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut612	ORF1a	C11344T	nsp6		Synonymous	Observed in 99 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut641	ORF1a	A12121T	nsp8		Synonymous	Observed in 57 countries. Most prevalent in Denmark followed by UK and USA.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut725	ORF1b	T15096C, Y	nsp12		Synonymous	Observed in 148 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by Denmark, USA and Germany.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut728	ORF1b	C15240*, T	nsp12		Synonymous	Observed in 213 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut761	ORF1b	C16349T	nsp13	S38L	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 69 countries. Most prevalent in USA followed by Sweden, Denmark and UK.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut820	ORF1b	T17385G	nsp13	D383E	Nonsynonymous	Observed in 22 countries. Most prevalent in India.	Not found in Literature
Karnataka	Mut864	ORF1b	T19053C	nsp14		Synonymous	Observed in 46 countries. Most prevalent in UK followed by South Africa.	Not found in Literature

Table S 16: The following Table contains detailed information of the mutations with unknown functional effects, which were predicted by our model to be significant. The table includes the Genomic location, amino acid substitution (if any), mutation type and global distribution of the mutations